

The project

AGROSUS will identify appropriate **tools and agroecological strategies to prevent and manage weeds in relevant crops**, in conventional, organic, and mixed farming, in all the **11 biogeographic regions** (Alpine, Anatolian, Arctic, Atlantic, Black Sea, Boreal, Continental, Macaronesian, Mediterranean, Pannonian and Steppic) of the EU and associated countries, with the aim to reduce reliance on synthetic herbicides and the correlated pressure on the environment.

AGROSUS will co-develop the tools and strategies for the most problematic weeds of the different regions and crops **in collaboration with stakeholders**, and the short, medium, and long-term impact of the agroecological strategies will be analysed from environmental and socio-economic perspectives.

Objectives

Establishment of cultural **mechanical, physical, biological, and biotechnological Agroecological System**.

Technology transfer and training for the prevention and management of weeds.

Promote the most appropriate **initiatives at the field, administration and regulatory levels**.

Advanced **detection tools**.

Expand knowledge on problematic weeds on European Agriculture.

Overarching objective

AGROSUS aims to provide **crop management tools** implementing techniques that allow sustainable, fair, and safe weed management in conventional, organic, and mixed farming systems, as well as fostering farmers' acceptance.

DURATION: June 2023 to May 2027 (**48 months**).

BUDGET: **4 999 863.75 €**. Funded by the European Union (**4 689 926.25 €**) and the Hungarian government (**309 937.50 €**).

CALL: **CL6-2022-FARM2FORK-02-01-two-stage**: Agroecological approaches for sustainable weed management.

PARTNERS: The AGROSUS project is coordinated by the Universidad de Vigo (UVIGO) from Spain and involves **16 partners from 11 European and associated countries**.

STAY TUNED!

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AGROSUS

AGROecological strategies for SUSTainable weed management in key European crops

Funded by the European Union

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Main results

- **Stakeholder network** actively participating in the decision and adoption of the agroecological strategies.
- Reports on **weed-associated problems**, including an updated **list of the most problematic weeds** in Europe and factors hindering agroecological approaches adoption.
- Guidelines about **best agroecological approaches** per crop and region through Europe.
- Demonstrative videos of **robots and drones' potential** for early weed detection targeted to farmers and advisors.
- **Reports** on agroecological approaches agronomic potential and delivery of ecosystem services.
- Reports on agroecological approaches **environmental and socio-economic impact**.
- **Stakeholder's recommendations** for agroecological approaches implementation in European agriculture.
- Network with stakeholders to foster **affiliated entities** acceptance through identification, discussion, and eventual policy changes to favour agroecological approaches.

Multi-actor approach

Stakeholders will provide the farm expertise, the local knowledge about problems to solve, and the feedback needed to steer research work towards tangible outcomes, with links to international organizations, research institutes, and farmer associations for sustainable agriculture.

For this, **14 Regional Stakeholder Communities (RSC)** and their **Crop-Linked Groups (24 CLG)** will be build around each experimental unit (at the regional level) covering the 11 biogeographic regions for **co-creation** and **co-validation** of actions undertaken during the project.

AGROSUS partners and stakeholders will co-design together -through **surveys, in-person interviews, workshops**- the agroecological strategies (for the assessment of the short-term impact) that will be implemented in each biogeographic region and will also co-validate the agroecological strategies collecting feedback -through workshops- to improve the strategies implemented in each biogeographic region.

In collaboration with stakeholders, AGROSUS will recognize the most commonly used herbicides, the most troublesome weeds and the problems encountered by farmers for their management in each of the 11 biogeographic European regions and will identify factors influencing **farmers' decision-making** hindering the adoption of agroecological approaches.

11 Biogeographical regions

14 Regional Stakeholders' Communities

24 Crop-linked Groups

19 Co-creation workshops

38 Co-validation workshops

68 Short-term farming systems

31 Crops

3 FARMING SYSTEM: Conventional, Organic, Mixed

10 ARABLE CROPS

Barley, Cotton, Maize, Oats, Potato, Rapeseed, Soybean, Sunflower, Triticale, Wheat

9 HORTICULTURAL CROPS

Aromatic plants - 3sp. (Vinca, Rumex, Plantago), Cabbage, Carrot, Lettuce, Melon, Tomato, Zucchini

12 PERENNIAL CROPS

Almond, Apple, Apricot, Berry, Custard apple, Hazelnut, Olive, Orange, Peach, Persimmon, Pistachio, Vineyard